

PRODUCTION READINESS VERIFICATION TESTING

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The Production Readiness Verification Testing (PRVT) program has been established, as the name implies, to determine if structures fabricated from advanced composite materials can be committed on a production basis to commercial airline service. Prior to a production commitment, questions pertaining to variation in static strength and long-term durability of structures which reflect the variabilities that can be realistically expected from current production and quality control technologies must be answered. These questions are being addressed in the PRVT program by testing twenty-two duplicates of each of two structural elements. These elements represent a segment of the front spar and cover of a vertical stabilizer box structure designed for the Lockheed L-1011 aircraft. Ten specimens of each element have been subjected to static strength tests and the other twelve of each type are currently undergoing long term durability testing. The durability tests are structured to simulate the loading and environmental exposure (temperature and humidity) representative of twenty years of service in a test period of three and one half years. This paper discusses the PRVT program and provides the results of the static tests and a durability assessment after one year of continuous load/environment testing.

INTRODUCTION

The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) has established programs under the Aircraft Energy Efficiency (ACEE) project office to accelerate the use of composite structures in production commercial transport aircraft. The Lockheed-California Company has two major advanced composite hardware development programs being performed under contract with the NASA, Langley Research Center. The two programs are for the development and fabrication of the vertical fin and inboard aileron of the Lockheed L-1011 transport aircraft from advanced composite materials. The Advanced Composite Vertical Fin (ACVF) and Advanced Composite Aileron (ACA) programs are scoped to provide a high level of confidence in the structural integrity and long-term durability of advanced composite structure. The ACVF program does not include flight service evaluation but alternately provides for multiple large-scale subcomponents of the ACVF structure for evaluation of variability in static strength and for assessment of durability under extended time laboratory tests involving both load and environment simulation.

The PRVT program utilizes subcomponents which reflect the variabilities in structure that can realistically be expected from current production and quality control technologies to provide information to answer the following questions:

- What is the range of production qualities that can be expected for components manufactured under conditions similar to those expected in production, and how realistic and effective are proposed quality standards and quality control procedures?
- What variability in static strength can be expected for production quality components and are the design allowables sufficient to account for this variability?
- Will production quality components survive laboratory fatigue tests involving both load and environment simulation of sufficient duration and severity to provide confidence in long-term durability in the service environment?

These questions are not primarily directed toward basic material properties. The questions are directed instead to the realities of production quality as influenced by cost objectives and by scale-up and complexity effects which will cause structural quality to differ from that represented by idealized small coupons.

Twenty-two duplicates of each of two key structural elements on the ACVF were fabricated for the PRVT program. One element represents the front spar to fuselage joint area, and the other represents the cover to fuselage joint area, see Fig. 1. These specimens were manufactured as near as practical under conditions anticipated for production hardware and then subjected to nondestructive inspection (NDI) procedures. Ten specimens of each type were subjected to static strength tests, and the other twelve of each type are currently undergoing durability tests.

PRODUCTION QUALITIES

The ACVF box structure, shown in Fig. 1 is approximately 7.6 meters long with a root box chord of 2.7 meters and an area of 13.9 square meters. The spars are fabricated from T300/5208 graphite-epoxy tape material. The spar web consists of 24 plies oriented at 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° at the root tapering to 12 plies at the tip. The outer plies of $\pm 45^\circ$ web material are utilized with pre-plyed 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ material to make up the spar caps. At the fuselage joint, the spar caps are tapered to provide an interface with the existing metallic components used for the fin-to-fuselage installation. Above the fuselage joint, the spar cap thickness tapers from 48 plies to 16 plies at the upper end of the spar. The spar segment utilized in the PRVT program represents the lower 2.1 meters of the front spar, see Fig. 2.

Figure 1. Advanced Composite Vertical Fin Configuration

Figure 2. PRVT Spar Component

The manufacturing process utilized in the production of the twenty-two spars consisted of molding the spars in a steel matched-die tool using a modified thermal elastomeric process. Caps, webs, stiffeners, and rib attachment angles are integrally consolidated and molded in an autoclave. The resin cure is completed by oven post-curing the spar.

Twenty-two spar components were fabricated to demonstrate repeatability of quality, structural integrity, and long term durability of composite material.

The quality control procedures and quality standards established for the spars were demonstrated to be both realistic and effective. Some minor discrepancies persisted in all 22 spars, but all of the spars produced were accepted for use in the PRVT program. Sequential inspections were provided during layup to ensure conformity with drawing and specification requirements. Verification of cure cycle parameters was accomplished by real-time monitoring of recording instrumentation throughout the cure cycle. Following post cure, visual and dimensional inspections were conducted after removal of resin flash and process control specimens. The specimens used for process control were taken from the discs cut from the spar web to form the access holes. The discs provided short beam shear, flexural, compression, specific gravity, resin content and porosity specimens. Each spar was nondestructively inspected using pulse-echo ultrasonic techniques. Through transmission ultrasonic dual transducers were used to further assess any indications found.

All of the spars fabricated had minor thickness and mark-off discrepancies, but none were serious enough for cause for rejection. The ultrasonic inspection indicated no voids or porosity in any of the spars. The test data obtained from the process control discs indicated consistent properties with acceptable scatter bands.

The covers of the ACVF are also fabricated from T300/5208 graphite-epoxy tape material as a single stage cure hat-stiffened skin. The skin consists of 34 plies oriented at 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ at the root end tapering to 10 plies at the tip. Additional plies are provided at the rib and spar attach areas to provide a reinforced bearing pad for countersunk fasteners. The hat stiffeners consist of 10 plies of material oriented at 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ with a 10 ply segment of 0° plies sandwiched in the hat crown. The cover component utilized in the PRVT program represents the lower aft portion of the cover, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3. PRVT Cover Component

The manufacturing process utilized in the production of the planned 22 covers consisted of autoclave curing the covers on a contoured tool. Inflatable rubber mandrels vented to autoclave pressure were utilized for cocuring the hat stiffeners to the skin. Both right hand and left hand covers were fabricated in order to accommodate the durability test requirement of testing the cover components in pairs.

As with the spars, twenty-two cover components were fabricated to achieve the objectives of this program. The quality control procedures and quality standards established for the covers were demonstrated to be both realistic and effective. The cover components each included a 18 centimeter extension at the upper end which was trimmed and sent to the Quality Assurance Laboratory. These panels were cut into coupons at several locations and tested for physical and mechanical properties. Throughout the various phases of fabrication, inspections were provided to ensure design and specification conformity. Verification of cure cycle

parameters was accomplished by real-time monitoring of recording instrumentation. After cure, each component was nondestructively inspected using through transmission ultrasonic techniques.

Some of the covers had minor thickness and mark-off discrepancies, but none were serious enough for rejection. Seven covers, however, were rejected and had to be replaced. The causes for rejection included trimming error, foreign material cocured with the component, and excessive void indication in the ultrasonic C-scan inspection. The voids were caused by improper tooling in a doubler area which was corrected. With this tooling correction, practically no voids or porosity were found in the covers accepted for test.

VARIABILITY IN STATIC STRENGTH

In order to determine the variability in static strength of composite structure, ten specimens each of the spar and cover components were tested to failure in a selected critical mode. The spars were loaded as cantilever beams with failure expected to initiate in the web in the lower bay through a lightening hole. The covers were loaded as columns with failure expected to initiate in the upper bay with buckling of the skin and subsequent crippling of the hat stiffeners. Both the spars and covers behaved as predicted in the static tests, with the cover components providing more consistent results.

All testing was performed at laboratory air temperature with the components in the as-fabricated condition. Subsequent examinations indicated that the spar components had, on the average, 0.6 percent by weight, moisture content and the cover components 0.5 percent. The specimens were tested randomly as no attempt was made to test them in the order of fabrication.

A typical static test setup for the spar components is shown in Fig. 4. Each spar component was installed in the same test fixture with care taken to ensure that each setup was identical. Loading was accomplished through the use of two hydraulic jacks located at the outboard end and at vertical stabilizer station (VSS), 121.45 to obtain the required bending moment and shear distributions. The required spar cap axial load distribution was obtained by providing aluminum straps mechanically fastened to the spar cap flanges to simulate effective cover material. For each test, the loads, strains and deflections were recorded by a data acquisition system. Each specimen was instrumented with six axial, five rosette strain gages, and five deflection transducers.

In general, the test procedure was identical for each spar component. Test loads were applied to design ultimate, maintained for 30 seconds, and then returned to zero. This procedure was performed for a second time, and then compared for repeatability. This comparison revealed no detectable variance in strain gage response to the loadings applied to each of the ten spar components tested. Test loads were then applied continuously until failure.

All spar failures occurred as predicted through the lightening hole inboard of VSS 121.45 as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. The results of all ten spar static tests are shown in Fig. 7. The results are plotted as percent of design ultimate load (DUL) versus component test sequence. The predicted failure load based on the results of coupon tests, is 120% DUL and the average test failure load is 135% DUL. The coefficient of variation for the spar components is 6.1%. All of the components failed at values above that predicted from coupon tests.

A typical test setup for the cover components is shown in Figs. 8 and 9. Each of the ten cover components was installed upside down in a static test machine. Every effort was made to ensure that the test setup and loading techniques were identical. For each test, the load strains and deflections were recorded by a data acquisition system. Each specimen was instrumented with eight axial strain gages and a single rosette strain gage. In addition to the strain gages, four deflection transducers were installed to measure loading head deflection as well as to provide a check on panel alignment in the test machine.

Figure 4. Spar Static Test Setup

Figure 5. Typical Spar Static Failure - Web Side

Figure 6. Typical Spar Static Failure - Stiffener Side

Figure 7. Spar Static Test Results

Figure 8. Typical Cover Static Test Setup - Skin Side

Figure 9. Typical Cover Static Test Setup - Stiffener Side

All ten static cover panels were loaded in compression under nominally identical conditions. Test loads were applied to 50 percent of DUL and then back to zero to check gage polarity and panel alignment. The loading was then taken to DUL and back to zero, repeated and then compared for repeatability. As with the spars, this comparison revealed no detectable variance in strain gage response to the loadings applied to each of the cover components tested. The compression test loads were then applied continually until failure.

With the exception of one specimen, all primary cover failures occurred as predicted in the upper bay, above VSS 121.45. The failures appeared to initiate at the center hat in the region where the skin is buckled outward as shown in Figs. 10 and 11. The remaining specimen failed in the lower, adjacent panel. The results of all ten cover static tests are given in Fig. 12 in the sequence tested. The predicted failure load for this panel, based on the results of coupon tests is 134% DUL and the average test failure load is 160% DUL. The coefficient of variation for the cover components is 3.3%. All of the cover components failed at values considerably higher than that predicted from coupon tests.

A similar program, to determine structural strength reproducibility of graphite/epoxy composite spoilers for the Boeing 737, has been conducted by the Boeing Aircraft Company [1]. In that program, fifteen spoilers were statically loaded to failure. The spoiler construction was graphite/epoxy skins bonded to aluminum honeycomb core. The spoilers tested in this investigation were among the last 25 of a production run of 140. All fifteen spoilers failed in the same mode; buckling of the lower skin and failure of the upper skin in tension. The average test failure load was 179% of DUL with a coefficient of variation for the spoiler components of 6.6 percent.

The variation in static strength of some common structural materials is shown in Table I. As indicated in this table, the coefficient of variation of graphite/epoxy material is comparable to that obtained for metallic materials.

Figure 10. Typical Cover Static Failure - Stiffener Side

Figure 11. Typical Cover Static Failure - Skin Side

Figure 12. Cover Static Test Results

Material	Component	No. Spec.	Loading	Coefficient of Variation Percent
Graphite-Epoxy	PRVT-Cover	10	Compression	3.3
Graphite-Epoxy	PRVT-Spar	10	Bending	6.1
Graphite-Epoxy	Spoiler [1]	15	Bending	6.6
Graphite-Epoxy	Laminate Coupons	411	Tension	5.7
Graphite-Epoxy	Laminate Coupons	411	Ten-Modulus	4.0
Graphite-Epoxy	Laminate Coupons	290	Compression	9.0
Graphite-Epoxy	Laminate Coupons	290	Compr-Modulus	5.2
Wood	Mosquito Wings [2]	5	Bending	10.3
Wood	Plywood Shear Wall [3]	27	Shear	9.7
Concrete	Test Cylinders [3]	216	Compression	10.6
Aluminum	7049-T73 Die Forging [4]	384	Tension	3.2
Aluminum	A357-T6 Casting [5]	804	Tension	5.5
Titanium	TI-SAL-2.5SN Sheet [6]	565	Tension	3.9
Steel	Structural Steel [3]	3982	Tension	7.1
Steel	17-7PH Sheet [6]	88	Tension	5.1

Table I. Coefficient of Variation in Static Strength of Some Structural Materials

LONG-TERM DURABILITY

The durability tests are structured to simulate the loading and environmental exposure (temperature and humidity) representative of twenty years of service in a test period of approximately three and one-half years. The durability tests are in process, with twelve cover and twelve spar components being evaluated.

Four durability chambers have been fabricated to accommodate the 24 test components. Two chambers are utilized to interrogate the twelve spar components and two chambers are used to interrogate the twelve cover components. A sketch of the spar chambers is shown in Fig. 13. Six spar components are mounted in each of the two chambers. The spars are mounted in pairs, each pair forming a box section. The spars are loaded as a cantilever box beam using a single jack located at the outboard end. The spar box section is shown in Fig. 14.

Figure 13. Spar Durability Test Chamber/Setup

A sketch of the cover chambers is shown in Fig. 15. Six cover components are mounted in each of the two chambers. The covers are mounted in pairs, each pair forming a closed box section. The cover box section is loaded axially through each cover and is designed for no transfer of load between the covers. The cover box section also permits the covers to be heated and cooled from the outside surface with the reverse side permitted to seek a cycle similar to that expected of the ACVF box interior. The cover box component is shown in Fig. 16.

The load and environment spectra being applied to the test components is shown in Fig. 17. This figure shows upper and lower bound test temperatures, relative humidities and flight load segments considered in defining the flight environmental and load profile.

The environmental/loading spectrum is applied continually 24 hours a day, 5 days a week. Repeating the spectrum will produce approximately 5800 thermal cycles in the three and one-half year test program. The upper bound of temperature of 333.1K was selected on the following basis. The thermal cycles being used in the test represent about 20% of the total cycles expected in the ACVF lifetime. The ambient temperature, then, was assumed to be that exceeded on the average of 20% of the time, or an ambient of 302.6K, based on temperature exceedance data.

Figure 14. Spar Durability Test Components

Figure 15. Cover Durability Test Chamber/Setup

Figure 16. Cover Durability Test Components

Figure 17. Loads and Environment Basic Loading Block

This ambient temperature converts to a skin temperature of 333.1K if a skin painted with a dark color is assumed. In addition to the given environmental spectrum, at convenient and dispersed times during the conduct of the test, the temperature/humidity is allowed to reach 344.3K/20% RH 40 times, and 355.4K/20% RH 10 times. The conditions simulate the maximum temperatures expected infrequently in service.

The lower bound to temperature of 238.7K was selected to be certain that the moisture in the laminates would be fully frozen prior to beginning the heating cycle. This would ensure the maximum volumetric expansion of the laminate, working

against the metal joint plates and fasteners. Further, in the fully-frozen state no moisture transfer takes place, so lower temperatures are of no significance to the test. The relative humidities were chosen at 0% and 95% in alternate cycles to exercise to the maximum the moisture gradients between layers of the laminate.

The environmental/loading spectrum shown in Fig. 17 is applied to the four chambers in a staggered sequence to accommodate the cool-down capabilities of the refrigeration system. With Chamber No. 1 (spar chamber) in operation Chamber No. 2 (spar chamber) start is delayed 75 minutes and the start of Chambers No's. 3 and 4 (cover chambers) is delayed 150 minutes. On weekends the four chambers are allowed to stabilize at approximately 297K and 100% humidity. Weekends are also kept available to add thermal cycles if such should be necessary.

Due to the compression of the thermal cycling, namely 5800 cycles simulating twenty years, 6.2 flights of loading cycles are applied per thermal cycle to simulate 36,000 flights in twenty years. Loading cycles occur only in the climb, cruise and descent phase of flight. In order to approximate the anticipated loading experience, 35% of the loading cycles are applied in each of the climb and descent phases of the flight, with 30% of the cycles in the cruise phase. The climb or descent loadings are applied while the skin temperature ranges from 300K to 277.6K, and the cruise loadings are applied while the temperature ranges from 255.4K to 238.7K. The more severe loadings (limit loads) are applied during climb or descent.

The chambers, test fixtures and control system have been designed to minimize the need for monitoring and maintenance during the course of the test. In particular, this includes computer control of loads and environment, malfunction devices for remote monitoring, premium quality load jacks to reduce down time and repairs, use of corrosion resistant material for chamber interiors and test fixtures, and a central environmental unit with a distribution system to each environmental chamber. The durability chambers for the spars and covers are shown in Figs. 18 and 19.

The limit strain being applied in the durability test as a result of the flight loadings is 2000 μ in/in. In order to investigate the effects of higher strain levels on durability of graphite/epoxy material, two each of the spar and cover components are being subject to 50% higher strains. This is being accomplished through the use of larger jacks. The center spar pairs in Chamber No. 1 and the center cover pair in Chamber No. 3 are the high strain test components.

Figure 18. Spar Durability Chamber

Figure 19. Cover Durability Chamber

Throughout the course of the durability testing each specimen is being inspected per field service inspection techniques. Any damage detected will be monitored for growth, or will be repaired using field service repair techniques, depending on extent and location of the damage. As of this date no damage has occurred. The high time spar chamber (Chamber No. 1) has completed over 1600 thermal cycles which is equivalent to over 5 years of flight service. The high time cover chamber (Chamber No. 4) has completed over 1200 thermal cycles which is equivalent to over 4 years of flight service. At the completion of the long-term durability tests, each component will be inspected and then subjected to residual strength static tests. The results of these tests will be compared to the results of the static test portion of this program to determine the effect of repeated loading and environmental cycling on the strength of advanced composite structures.

CONCLUSION

Two of the three questions which were posed at the beginning of this paper have been answered in the PRVT program. The third question is in the process of being satisfied. The first question dealt with production qualities of advanced composite structures. The fabrication of over 44 large components has provided assurance that consistently high quality parts can be expected for composite structure manufactured under a production environment. In addition, the quality standards established in the process specifications are both realistic and achievable, and the quality control procedures are effective.

The second question dealt with variation in static strength. The coefficient of variation of 6.1% obtained from testing ten spar components and 3.3% obtained from testing ten cover components indicate the variability in static strength that can be expected from production parts. These values are comparable to that obtained from metallic structures.

The third question relates to the durability of composites which is in the process of being answered. After an equivalent of 4 years of intensive load/temperature/humidity testing the only problems encountered relate to keeping the metallic components/equipment operational.

In conclusion, the PRVT program has demonstrated that structures fabricated from graphite/epoxy material can be of consistent high quality, will exhibit little variation in static strength, and has so far demonstrated durability in the service environment.

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